

A Pathway to General-Purpose Scientific AI: Multimodal Comprehension of Scientific Images

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Abstract—Modern scientific communication is highly visual, yet current digital libraries and AI systems remain largely text-centric. While vision-language models (VLMs) such as GPT-4V and Gemini achieve impressive results on general benchmarks, recent evaluations show that they falter on scientific figures, struggling with multi-step reasoning, spatial inference, and domain-specific interpretation. This gap limits the ability of digital libraries to index, retrieve, and analyze the rich knowledge embedded in charts, plots, and other scientific images. In this poster, we present a position on advancing multimodal scientific AI and introduce our ongoing project ALD/E-ImageMiner. The project develops a gold-standard dataset from atomic layer deposition and etching literature, annotated for four complementary tasks: chart type classification, data table extraction, chart-to-text summarization, and question answering. By enabling multi-task evaluation on domain-specific images, ALD/E-ImageMiner provides a rigorous benchmark for assessing and improving VLMs in specialized scientific contexts. We further argue for a long-term vision of “scientific conceptual understanding from images” as a new benchmark for AI in digital libraries, moving beyond surface-level perception to genuine comprehension of the scientific insights conveyed by visual artifacts. This work contributes a concrete dataset and a broader agenda for transforming digital libraries into truly multimodal knowledge infrastructures.

Index Terms—scientific images, multimodal AI, vision-language models, digital libraries, benchmarks, scientific reasoning

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern scientific communication is profoundly visual, with researchers regularly conveying critical information through various visual artifacts like charts, spectra, microscopic images, and experimental schematics. For the digital libraries and related technology community, this presents a significant challenge and opportunity: *how can our systems effectively manage, index, and make discoverable the rich knowledge embedded within these visual components?* To build robust general-purpose AI systems capable of scientific reasoning – which are becoming increasingly integral to next-generation digital libraries and research tools – these systems must interpret such visual artifacts with the same depth and accuracy as human experts. A key capability of future scientific AI assistants will be extracting and reasoning over scientific

information in both visual and textual forms – for example, from interpreting spectroscopic graphs to understanding laboratory apparatus diagrams [1]. Much of the nuance and quantitative data in science, such as trends in plots or features in micrographs, is often present only in figures, not solely in text. Consequently, without the ability to parse and analyze scientific images, an AI’s scientific understanding, and thus its utility in digital library applications for scholarly analysis, remains incomplete.

Despite the impressive language skills of large language models (LLMs), current systems are largely blind to visual content, severely limiting their effectiveness in scientific domains that rely heavily on images [2]. This visual deficit directly impacts the ability of digital libraries to provide comprehensive access and advanced services for scientific content. Even state-of-the-art multimodal models (e.g., GPT-4 Vision [3] or other Vision-Language Models, VLMs) struggle with scientific figures unless specifically trained for them. For instance, while LLMs excel in text-based medical knowledge, they have been observed to struggle to interpret medical images [4], hampering tasks like medical image question answering. In digital-library research, while emerging systems like ORKGEx [5] are beginning to integrate vision-language AI for scholarly content extraction and have shown promise with figure classification and summarization, they are still early proof-of-concept and limited in domain specificity and integration into automated pipelines. Therefore, a general AI scientist, vital for the future of digital scholarly infrastructure, must overcome this visual deficit to, for example, read a graph from a chemistry paper, extract the underlying data or trend, and grasp the scientific conclusion the image illustrates.

In summary, empowering AI with the ability to extract and understand scientific data from images is critical for robust scientific reasoning and for the evolution of digital libraries into truly multimodal knowledge repositories. This capability would unlock a more comprehensive understanding of research literature, which often pairs text with figures, and enable advanced applications essential for digital science infrastructure, such as automated experiment analysis, visual literature reviews, and multimodal question answering within digital library environments. Our work, exemplified by the ALD/E-ImageMiner project, directly addresses these gaps by creating domain-specific benchmarks to push the frontier of

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scientific image understanding, offering a valuable resource to the digital libraries, AI, and scientific communities. The remainder of this paper will discuss the current limitations of multimodal systems in this regard, describe a concrete effort to push the frontier of scientific image understanding, and outline future needs – culminating in a vision for “scientific conceptual understanding from images” as a new benchmark for AI.

II. RELATED WORK: GAPS IN SCIENTIFIC IMAGE UNDERSTANDING

A. Chart Understanding Datasets

Recent chart QA benchmarks have advanced research on visual data interpretation, but most use synthetic or general-purpose data. For instance, FigureQA [6] and DVQA [7] contain programmatically generated charts with template questions. PlotQA [8] provides millions of questions on automatically generated plots, and StructChart’s SimChart9K offers a large set of synthetic chart/table pairs from a language-model-driven simulator [9]. Even the ChartQA benchmark [10], which introduced 20,882 real charts with human-authored questions, focuses on broad, web-sourced topics (e.g. economic and survey charts) rather than domain-specific scientific plots. In summary, these datasets have advanced chart QA, but they primarily reflect generic visualizations and do not capture the specialized figures commonly found in scientific literature.

B. Limits of VLMs in Scientific Reasoning

Studies of modern vision-language models reveal that, despite strong perceptual abilities, these systems struggle with complex scientific inference. For example, the MaCBench benchmark [1] evaluates VLMs on chemistry and materials science tasks. Leading models achieved near-perfect scores on routine tasks (e.g. identifying lab equipment or extracting numeric values), but “exhibit fundamental limitations in spatial reasoning, cross-modal information synthesis, and multi-step logical inference.” In other words, current VLMs (and VLLMs) can often recognize basic chart elements, but fail on reasoning that requires understanding the spatial layout or combining visual data across modalities. These results suggest that chart and figure understanding in scientific contexts – which frequently demands multi-step logic – remains beyond the reach of off-the-shelf multimodal models.

Beyond chemistry-specific benchmarks, many studies report that current VLMs lack robust reasoning capabilities. Campbell et al. (2024) show that even top models (including GPT-4V [3]) fail on very simple multi-object visual reasoning tasks (e.g. counting objects, basic analogies) that humans solve effortlessly [11]. Similarly, Jiang et al. (2025) introduce the MAC benchmark [12], a live benchmark constructed from journal covers and cover stories across Nature, Science, and Cell. Their results show that while VLMs demonstrate strong perceptual recognition, they rely heavily on textual cues and struggle with deeper cross-modal scientific reasoning, particularly when visual text is removed. In essence, modern vision-language models are very good at perceptual recognition

but often “swear blind” on spatial and relational problems. These findings are consistent with the “binding problem” in visual reasoning and echo both MaCBench and MAC: VLMs generally cannot reliably perform complex spatial or multi-step logical inference.

C. VLMs in scientific knowledge tools

In digital-library research, emerging systems have begun to integrate vision-language AI for scholarly content extraction. For instance, Hussein et al. (2025) introduce ORKGEx, a browser-based annotation tool that uses LLMs and VLMs to help extract structured research contributions into the Open Research Knowledge Graph [5]. They point out that scientific articles contain complex figures that traditional OCR cannot decode (charts have intertwined text and graphical elements). To address this, ORKGEx employs recent vision-language transformers (e.g. ViT-based chart models) to parse figures: “state-of-the-art Vision Transformers (ViT) and Vision-Language Models (VLMs) such as UniChart and LLaVa...have shown great results on figure classification, chart-to-table, and figure summarization” [5]. Such tools are early examples of leveraging multimodal AI for structured scientific knowledge curation, but remain largely proof-of-concept and are not yet tuned to specific domains or integrated into fully automated pipelines.

D. Recent Vision-Language Models

Recent large vision-language models (VLMs) and multimodal large language models (MLLMs) have achieved striking progress on general benchmarks, but specialized evaluations reveal critical shortcomings on scientific imagery. GPT-4V and Gemini, for instance, perform well on broad captioning and VQA, yet careful comparisons show that GPT-4V favors concise precision while Gemini tends toward detailed but verbose outputs, with both struggling on table reasoning and formula recognition [13]. Systematic benchmarks sharpen this picture: ChartInsights [14] shows GPT-4V peaking at only 56% accuracy on low-level chart analysis tasks, and even advanced prompting strategies (“Chain-of-Charts,” visual overlays) only raise performance to ~84%. Similarly, FlowLearn [15] demonstrates that GPT-4V achieves 58% on flowchart node counting while Claude excels at OCR, but no single model performs reliably across tasks. These findings indicate that even state-of-the-art closed models fail at the fine-grained analysis required for scientific figures.

Beyond charts and diagrams, broader evaluations confirm these limitations. SalBench [16] shows that models including GPT-4o fail at odd-one-out saliency detection, achieving below 50% accuracy on tasks trivial for humans, a clear manifestation of Moravec’s paradox. Reinforcement learning-based approaches such as G1 [17] illustrate that perception and reasoning can bootstrap one another in interactive environments, but these remain far removed from robust scientific reasoning. Domain-specific tuning offers partial gains: Visual Instruction Tuning [18] enables open-source models like LLaVA to reach

~85% of GPT-4’s multimodal performance, while LLaVA-Med [19] leverages biomedical figures to outperform prior medical VQA baselines, yet still hallucinates details and misses multi-step logic. Finally, benchmarks targeting higher-level scientific reasoning further emphasize gaps: MaCBench [1] shows strong perception but failures in spatial and logical inference, while MAC [12], built from journal covers of *Nature*, *Science*, and *Cell*, reveals heavy overreliance on textual cues—performance collapses once cover text is removed.

In summary, while modern VLMs excel at surface-level perception, they consistently falter on structured scientific reasoning across modalities. To move beyond these limitations, we present our ongoing project **ALD/E-ImageMiner**, which focuses on a narrow scientific subdomain—atomic-layer deposition and etching research—and provides gold-standard annotations for each figure. The dataset supports multi-task evaluation on the same images, covering chart classification, precise data extraction, textual summarization, and question answering. By coupling domain-specific figures with rich annotations across tasks, ALD/E-ImageMiner fills a critical gap in prior work and enables rigorous assessment of VLMs’ capabilities in specialized scientific contexts. This comprehensive, domain-focused benchmark is designed to catalyze progress where existing datasets and models fall short.

III. ALD/E-IMAGEMINER: DOMAIN-SPECIFIC SCIENTIFIC IMAGE DATASET

To address the identified gap, we are developing the **ALD/E-ImageMiner project**—an annotation initiative focused on scientific images in the domain of Atomic Layer Deposition/Etching (ALD/E). ALD/E is a subfield of materials science and engineering where research papers frequently include technical figures, particularly thin-film growth plots and process-related charts. The project aims to create a high-quality, expert-annotated dataset drawn from approximately 200 ALD/E research articles (covering about 600 figures). It concentrates on 18 distinct chart categories (e.g., bar, line, scatter, pie), ensuring systematic coverage of result-plot types that are central to the field. By concentrating on a single domain, the dataset captures visual patterns and semantics often overlooked by general-purpose models. The ALD/E-ImageMiner dataset, led by the author, will directly support and benchmark multimodal AI in scientific image comprehension.

Each figure in the dataset is annotated for multiple complementary tasks, reflecting the range of capabilities a general-purpose AI scientist should have:

- **Chart Type Classification:** Identify the type of chart or visual (among 18 categories) to determine how information is encoded. This is a foundational step for downstream interpretation.
- **Data Table Extraction (DTE):** Reconstruct the underlying data table from the chart image. For example, given a plotted curve or bar chart, the system extracts the numeric values and labels represented. This transforms visual plots

back into machine-readable data, enabling verification and reuse of quantitative results.

- **Chart-to-Text Summarization (CTS):** Generate a concise textual summary of the chart’s key insights. The summary describes trends, patterns, or comparisons shown in the figure (e.g., “the growth rate increases rapidly in the first 5 cycles and then plateaus”), akin to how an expert would summarize a figure for a colleague.
- **Chart Question Answering (QA):** Answer research questions based on the figure, requiring logical reasoning over the visual data. For instance, an annotator might ask, “What was the average growth in the first ALD cycle shown in the plot?”, and the answer must be derived from the figure. This tests the system’s ability to not only read the chart but also understand it in context to produce correct, relevant answers.

By providing annotations for all four tasks on the same set of images, ALD/E-ImageMiner offers a rich **multimodal testbed**. An AI model can be trained to perform chart classification, data extraction, summarization, and QA in an integrated fashion. We expect that this holistic, multi-task learning setup will push models closer to genuine *understanding* of scientific figures, as opposed to excelling at a single narrow task. Moreover, focusing on a specialized domain like ALD/E ensures the inclusion of domain-specific terminology and conventions in figures, which will help in evaluating how well models can adapt their vision-language capabilities to particular scientific contexts. The resulting dataset (and benchmark tasks) will be made publicly available, providing a valuable resource to the digital libraries, AI, and scientific communities. It directly **fills the need for a domain-specific scientific image benchmark** and will complement existing general-purpose chart datasets.

IV. TOWARD “SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING” FROM IMAGES: A GRAND CHALLENGE

While projects like ALD/E-ImageMiner represent a concrete step forward in addressing domain-specific scientific image understanding, our ultimate vision is far broader and critically relevant to the digital libraries community and by extension to the JCDL community. We advocate for “scientific conceptual understanding from images” as a new frontier and benchmark for AI within digital libraries. This goes beyond merely extracting textual data or numbers from figures; it means an AI can truly grasp the scientific concepts and insights that a human expert would infer from an image. For instance, a conceptually intelligent AI operating within a digital library system should recognize the scientific methodology illustrated in a complex experimental setup diagram or perceive phenomena of interest in a multilayer microscopy image. In essence, the goal is an AI that understands what a figure means in the context of scientific knowledge, not just what it looks like.

Achieving this profound level of comprehension would enable transformative applications in digital science infrastructure, fundamentally reshaping how digital libraries operate and deliver value. Future digital libraries and knowledge graph

platforms could automatically index and relate information from figures, moving beyond captions or surrounding text to truly integrate visual evidence into their knowledge bases. An AI with conceptual image understanding could perform *visual literature reviews* – analyzing figures across papers hosted in various digital library collections to identify trends or contradictions in experimental results. Such systems could assist in *automated experiment planning* by interpreting prior apparatus diagrams available in digital repositories and suggesting improvements. Moreover, these advanced AI systems would be able to answer complex multimodal questions, like “Compare the temperature-pressure phase diagram in Paper A with the one in Paper B – what differences in physical behavior are evident, and why might they occur?”, drawing upon the holistic visual and textual content within digital library holdings.

Realizing this vision will require significant advances: larger and more diverse multimodal scientific datasets, novel model architectures that integrate visual and symbolic reasoning, and standardized benchmarks to evaluate conceptual understanding. We propose that **scientific image understanding – the ability for AI to read and reason about figures as fluidly as text – should become a key benchmark for AI intelligence and a grand challenge for the *DL community in the coming years.** This means expanding efforts like ALD/E-ImageMiner to other domains (chemistry, engineering, physics, etc.) and developing evaluation tasks that necessitate cross-figure reasoning and deep comprehension. Success in this area would mark a significant milestone: general-purpose AI that can fully participate in scientific discovery by learning not only from written knowledge but also from the rich visual evidence found throughout scholarly communication preserved in digital libraries.

V. CONCLUSION

Empowering AI to **see and understand** scientific images is pivotal for the next generation of research tools and digital libraries. It bridges a critical gap in today’s language-centric AI models, bringing us closer to AI systems that truly comprehend and contribute to science. We specifically call upon the digital library community to recognize scientific image data extraction and understanding as a grand challenge – one that is essential for building comprehensive, multimodal digital knowledge repositories and ultimately, for achieving a more holistic AI capable of scientific reasoning on par with human experts. The work presented here is a step in that direction, envisioning it as part of a broader movement toward general-purpose scientific AI that learns from all forms of scholarly information accessible through advanced digital library systems.

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